

The role of converged satellite and terrestrial backhauling for 5G networks

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Abstract— The inter-operation of satellite and terrestrial backhauling can prove to be an efficient method to satisfy the increased demand in backhauling needs for the next generation of 5G technology. This paper reports the means for undertaking the task to satisfy the high needs of backhauling in terms of throughput. As it is reported this can be achieved by exploiting the concurrent use of millimeter wave wireless systems along with satellites in order to increase the bit rate of the transmitted traffic.

Keywords—SANSa project; 5G; architecture design; hybrid network manager (HNM);

I. INTRODUCTION

The SANSa project [1] aims to design, develop and showcase a novel self-reconfigurable hybrid terrestrial-satellite backhaul network operating at the microwave region (Ka band) based on the following key principles:

- Interoperation of satellite with terrestrial backhaul networks
- A terrestrial wireless network capable of reconfiguring its topology according to traffic demands
- Spectrum sharing between satellite and terrestrial segments.

Satellite benefits: the integration of the satellite component with the terrestrial backhaul network will be able to provide coverage and also overall capacity increase. It can provide large cells of coverage for relieving the terrestrial bottlenecks coming not only from real data but also from signaling and management. Besides, it also provides a new path for routing the traffic that increases the network resilience against link failures or congestion. It can also route intelligently the traffic to different routes by caching high definition video terrestrially and thus increase the QoE perceived by a user. Therefore, several satellite terminals can be deployed throughout the backhaul network by giving more flexibility to the hybrid network and providing more backup solutions.

Re-configurability benefits: The re-configurability process can allow traffic to be routed to less congested links which results in a capacity increase and also can provide a network resilience when a terrestrial link is failing.

Spectrum sharing between satellite and wireless backhaul nodes: Frequency spectrum is a scarce resource, therefore sharing the spectrum between two different technologies is

very important and should be an efficient way for throughput increase. SANSa is focused its research effort on Ka band where terrestrial backhauling bands of 18 GHz and 28 GHz are shared with the satellite-to-Earth and Earth-to-satellite satellite bands, respectively. The choice of this frequency bands has been made because these bands are already used in both terrestrial and satellite communications and current regulation already allows coexistence. However, SANSa solution will be easily exportable to other frequency bands.

Although the SANSa solution presents some benefits with respect to the aforementioned backhaul technologies, it is not orthogonal to them so it can be envisaged that a combination of all these solutions will address the backhaul networks challenges of the next generation services proposed by 5G.

Therefore, developing a sharing framework that will enable both satellite and mobile wireless nodes to cooperate for efficient transport of data in the frequency bands of 18GHz and 28GHz for download and upload respectively is of high interest. This work presents capacity graphs for the above frequencies for the terrestrial wireless links and describes how they can be used to improve the backhauling means of the future networks. In addition it presents the SANSa prototype which is proposed to achieve the previous objectives.

II. SIMULATION DATA

Typical data rate simulation graphs were considered by utilizing the following link budget figures for a link at 28GHz frequency.

Table II-1: Typical wireless data used for the simulation

Link type	Point-to-Point
Frequency	28GHz
Bandwidth	28MHz
Transmit Power	22dBm
Modulation	16 QAM
Antenna Diameter	0.3m-om3m
Antenna efficiency	0.65
Noise Temperature	290K
Rain rate	40mm/hour
LA	0.3dB
Receive Sensitivity	-78.5dBm
Distance	From 1km to 4km

Figure II-1: Total loss to distance

Key values of the loss with respect to distance is shown in the following table II-2.

Table II-2: Distance vs total loss

Distance (km)	Total Loss (dB)
1	129.5
2	138.5
3	143.8
4	147.5

The fade margin is shown in the following figure II-2

Figure II-2: Fade margin

Lastly the data rate with respect to the distance is shown in figure II-3

Figure II-3: Data rate vs distance

For clarity reasons, data from the above graph is presented in the following table

Table II-2: Data rate vs distance of terrestrial links

Distance (km)	Data rate (10 ⁸ bit/sec)
1	3.3
2	2.5
3	2.0
4	1.6

Regarding satellite throughputs values of the order of 2.5Gbps have been anticipated to be reached by 2020 by high throughput satellites for downlink with a modulation of 256 APSK.

The above data of terrestrial and satellite links show that high data rates can be transported especially when satellite and wireless backhaul links are sharing the spectrum for efficient backhauling means.

III. SANSa PROTOTYPE

The SANSa prototype that is going to evaluate the means for transporting effectively high bit rate data is shown in Figure III-1. It consists of an intelligent backhaul node (iBN) that can direct the beam to the best direction, mitigate interference and increase throughput and a hybrid network manager (HNM) which has an overview of the network and commands the above elements to perform effectively.

Figure III-1: SANSa prototype

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this extended abstract, we investigate design aspects of SANSa architectural prototype which will enable the seamless transport of high bit rate data. In addition the channel characteristics at the 28GHz frequency is presented.

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REFERENCES

- [1] *Shared Access Terrestrial-Satellite Backhaul Network enabled by Smart Antennas*, EU H2020 project, contract 645047

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